

Consistency in drug combination synergy scoring

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In this response, we first address Dr. Tang's concerns and then describe a comparative analysis of drug combination synergy evaluation using three software packages; our SynergyFinder 3.0, Dr. Tang's SynergyFinderPlus and another prominent tool in the drug combination discovery field, Combenefit. This comparison confirms consistency in the drug combination synergy scoring. We note that SynergyFinder 3.0 is the newest version of our web-tool (<https://synergyfinder.fimm.fi/>), and version 2.0 is not supported anymore. Importantly, there has never been an error in the codes of the SynergyFinder, nor in the operation of the web-tool (either v2.0 or v3.0). To avoid any confusion among the users, we below clarify the implementation aspects of the synergy scoring, which are fully detailed in the SynergyFinder user documentation online (https://synergyfinder.fimm.fi/synergy/synfin_docs/).

We and others working on the field are aware that the sign preceding the final term in the Bliss independence equation depends on the number of drugs (N) involved in the combination. This is not a novel discovery. For an odd N, the sign before the last term is positive, while for an even N, the sign is negative. In the SynergyFinder 2.0 paper, we presented the extended formula and showed the odd case as an example, making the positive (+) sign appropriate in this specific case. As was stated in the erratum note, that considered the even N case, our code implementation accounts for this sign change, hence ensuring that all the analyses performed with SynergyFinder are accurate.

The synergy model formulations presented in the SynergyFinder 2.0 paper did not cover all the situations, because of the page limit of the web-server issue manuscripts, and therefore we would like to direct Dr. Tang and other users to the exact formulations of each synergy model under different combination cases, which can be found online at https://synergyfinder.fimm.fi/synergy/synfin_docs/#reference.

More specifically, SynergyFinder codes make use of an alternative Bliss and ZIP synergy score implementation that does not require the selection of +/- sign before the last term, while yielding the same and consistent results:

$$S_{Bliss} = E_{A,B,\dots,N} - 100 \left(1 - \left(1 - \frac{E_A}{100} \right) \left(1 - \frac{E_B}{100} \right) \dots \left(1 - \frac{E_N}{100} \right) \right),$$
$$S_{ZIP} = \bar{E}_{A,B,\dots,N} - 100 \left(1 - \left(1 - \frac{\bar{E}_A}{100} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\bar{E}_B}{100} \right) \dots \left(1 - \frac{\bar{E}_N}{100} \right) \right).$$

Here, S_{Bliss} and S_{ZIP} are the Bliss and ZIP synergy scores, respectively, and E_N and $E_{A,B,\dots,N}$ are the experimentally measured single-drug and combination responses, while \bar{E}_N and $\bar{E}_{A,B,\dots,N}$ are the fitted responses.

As for the consistency concerning the Loewe model, we note that in the SynergyFinder 2.0

paper, Loewe additivity combination index (CI) calculation was reported, instead of Loewe synergy score, which may have confused Dr. Tang and other readers. However, it is essential to clarify that across all the versions of SynergyFinder tool, both in the code, implementation and documentation of the web-tool, we report the Loewe synergy score and not CI. For the calculation of Loewe synergy score, we make use of the exact implementation to which Dr. Tang refers:

$$S_{LOEWE} = E_{A,B,\dots,N} - E_{LOEWE},$$

where E_{LOEWE} satisfies the constraint $\sum_{k=A,B,\dots,N} \left(\frac{x_k}{f_k^{-1}(E_{LOEWE})} \right) = 1$; here, S_{LOEWE} represents Loewe synergy score, $E_{A,B,\dots,N}$ are the experimentally measured combination responses, x_A, x_B, \dots, x_N are doses of drugs A, B, \dots, N , and f_k^{-1} is the inverse of log-logistic model for a drug k . For more details, please refer to the Loewe section of the SynergyFinder documentation: https://synergyfinder.fimm.fi/synergy/synfin_docs/#reference.

We do take reproducibility very seriously when implementing computational tools and making them available for the end-users. This is why the SynergyFinder version 3.0 introduced a number of novel features that improve the consistency and reproducibility of drug combination synergy analyses, including a novel consensus synergy score that combines results from multiple synergy scoring models (1).

We unfortunately had to remove the SynergyFinder 3.0 codes from GitHub, since Dr. Tang duplicated our website without our permission and started to promote his own version of the web-tool. We find this kind of behavior very unfortunate for open-science.

Our SynergyFinder remains freely available online, without any login requirements. Moreover, we take a great pride in providing a comprehensive support to all the users of our tool, including > 40,000 users who have already utilized SynergyFinder web-tool to date. The unrestricted access to SynergyFinder 3.0, and its easy-to-use synergy scoring reports, enables researchers to evaluate its reproducibility and to compare its results with those generated by other drug synergy analysis tools, like we demonstrate below.

Comparison of the result from SynergyFinder 3.0, SynergyFinderPlus, and Combenefit

To cross-compare the analysis results of SynergyFinder 3.0, SynergyFinderPlus, and Combenefit tools for drug synergy analysis, we first compiled a drug combination dataset by integrating example data from these tools, including both 2-drug and 3-drug combinations. Notably, Combenefit does not implement the ZIP synergy score and is limited to HSA (highest single-agent), Bliss, and Loewe models only. Moreover, Combenefit does not support calculations for combinations with more than two drugs, resulting in a more limited comparison with Combenefit. As illustrated in Figure 1, there is a strong correlation between the synergy scores generated by these three tools.

Figure 1. Correlation of synergy scores calculated with SynergyFinder 3.0 and SynergyFinderPlus (panel a), and SynergyFinder 3.0 and Combeneft tools (panel b). A total of 52 synergy scores were calculated for 13 drug combinations, obtained by integrating example data from SynergyFinder 3.0 (five 2-drug and one 3-drug combinations), SynergyFinderPlus (two 2-drug and two 3-drug combinations), and Combeneft (three 2-drug combinations).

This comparative analysis confirms that the three implementations provide highly consistent results, ensuring that researchers can confidently utilize any of the implementations in drug synergy studies for analyzing their data and for obtaining robust and reproducible conclusions. We would like to emphasize that SynergyFinder 3.0 offers an array of advanced features and options not found in any other tools, including post-analysis capabilities, machine-learning-driven outlier detection and correction, interactive multi-sample analysis, and more, making SynergyFinder 3.0 a state-of-the-art tool in the field of drug combination discovery (3). The new features of our web-tool are expected to improve the consistency of drug combinations screens, accelerate the discovery of synergistic combinations, and enhance the translatability of discovered combinations into the clinic.

To provide the users with more details of the synergy scoring, we have made a comprehensive update of the SynergyFinder 3.0 documentation by adding more detailed information on the synergy calculations in various cases, and by providing examples of the synergy calculations. The updated content is now available online under the "Reference models" section of the technical documentation at https://synergyfinder.fimm.fi/synergy/synfin_docs/#reference. This update is intended to provide greater clarity for the synergy calculations, even for users who may not have a mathematical background. We will remain committed to improving our user documentation to provide the best guidance and experience for all the users of our SynergyFinder web-tool.

We are grateful for the possibility to address the concerns of Dr. Tang, and clarify the misunderstandings in the drug synergy analyses. We hope these clarifications will eliminate any confusion and ensure that the users fully understand how to best apply the synergy scores in their

research. As we continue to improve our SynergyFinder web-tool, we are confident that it will remain a valuable resource for researchers worldwide in drug combination discovery.

Conflict of Interest

Dr. Tang was a postdoc in the Aittokallio group, where the SynergyFinder tool is being developed. Subsequently, Dr. Tang established his own group, and started developing his own version of the tool and named it SynergyFinderPlus.

References

1. Ianevski A., Giri A.K., Aittokallio T. SynergyFinder 3.0: an interactive analysis and consensus interpretation of multi-drug synergies across multiple samples. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2022;50(W1):W739-W743.